

LEARNING MODULE IN BIOLOGY FOR SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

In the implementation of Republic Act No. 10533, the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum of 2013 or the K to 12 program problems such as lack of learning materials has become a burden not only to students but teachers. Due to this problem, students' low achievement and performance in science have been documented for years. Thus, this study was conducted to develop a learning module in biology for senior high school students. Biology is essential to students' holistic education, improving student performance in this subject is important. As such, the study assesses students' performance in areas such as biological molecules, energy transformation, genetics, and evolutionary relationships. The research also assesses how teachers use learning activities to meet performance standards in each area. It also evaluated the school heads/science coordinators and teachers on the effectiveness of the learning activities and discovered significant differences between the two groups. Descriptive method of research was adopted to collect data using a researcher-made questionnaire, interviews, and documentary analysis. Based on the findings, the students performed very satisfactory in energy transformation, while satisfactory in biological molecules, genetics, and evolutionary relationships. The results also showed that teachers utilized video presentations, brainstorming, and illustrations to help students meet the performance standards in various areas of biology. Thus, school heads and teachers considered video presentations and brainstorming as effective learning activities in biology classes. Moreover, the research also found a significant difference in the effectiveness of the learning activities between school heads and teachers. Furthermore, learning module consisting of learning competencies, objectives, varying learning activities, pre-test and post-test was designed to enhance students' performance in biology.

Keywords: biology, learning activities, learning module, senior high school